

DEVELOPING LEADERSHIP POTENTIALS OF SUPREME PUPIL GOVERNMENT IN PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

The Student Pupil Government (SPG) implements relevant programs, projects and activities in Philippine schools as mandated by the department. This study assessed the performance of SPG officers in Area 3, Division of Batangas with the end view of proposing a plan of activities to enhance their leadership potentials. This study covered the assessment on how SPG officers performed the assigned duties along with planning, implementation, monitoring and evaluation. Likewise, this also dealt on the SPG advisers' mentoring activities and even described the leadership qualities and potentials of SPG officers. Moreover, the issues and challenges encountered that bear significant impact in the leadership of SPG officers were also identified. The descriptive method of research was utilized in the study with the use of a questionnaire as the main data gathering instrument. Interview and focus group discussion were conducted to enrich the findings of the study. Respondents included 148 school heads and 148 SPG advisers from Area III, Division of Batangas Province. Results from the findings revealed that the SPG officers need improvement in skills of planning of activities conducted in schools. Also, SPG advisers should continue working together with SPG officers to ensure effective implementation and coordination among school officials and student body. Leadership qualities and potentials are remarkable among SPG officers. Concerns on administrative support and cooperation are the topmost issue and challenge which affect SPG officers' leadership. The proposed plan of activities may be relevant resources for enhancement of SPG officers' competencies and performance.

Keywords: leadership potentials, leadership qualities, plan of activities, student leaders, student government, supreme pupil government, focus group discussion, mentoring